

COMPOSITION OF FERRIC ARSENITE AND FERROUS ARSENATE.
PART III. ANALYSIS OF THE SO-CALLED FERROUS ARSENATE
PRODUCT OF MIXING FeSO_4 AND Na_2HAsO_4

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Qualitative experiments have shown that mutual oxidation and reduction take place between ferrous sulphate and Na_2HAsO_4 only in acid solution. The percentage of arsenite was, however, estimated quantitatively by the method adopted in the analysis of the precipitates obtained by mixing FeCl_3 with NaAsO_2 (Part II of the series). From the results of the analysis, the composition of the precipitates obtained by mixing FeSO_4 and Na_2HAsO_4 was found to be more variable with conditions. The composition of the product shows greater similarity when the mixed reactants are allowed to age for several weeks.

To study the composition of the precipitates, qualitative study of the filtrate from samples obtained by mixing the reactants in aqueous, neutral and acidified solutions was made as was done in the case of mixing FeCl_3 with NaAsO_2 (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 47). It was observed that on mixing aqueous solution of ferrous sulphate and Na_2HAsO_4 , a greenish white precipitate was immediately obtained which darkened in colour when left overnight. The precipitate sets to a jelly-like mass. The filtrate is clear and colourless at first but gradually shows a white turbidity; it contains enough ferrous sulphate and is distinctly acidic, showing that the reaction is not quantitative according to the simplest equation

The compound is oxidised on heating and it changes from green to dark brown due to oxidation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Merck's samples of $\text{Na}_2\text{HAsO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used and the solution was standardised iodometrically against sodium thiosulphate of known strength. Merck's sample of ferrous sulphate was recrystallised in alcohol and the dried sample was kept in a desiccator. Its solution was standardised against potassium permanganate as usual.

The reactants were then mixed in equivalent proportions and the precipitate was filtered in a Buchner funnel by filter pump, and washed free from sulphate. The precipitate was dried by placing the Buchner funnel over a chimney and in an air-oven at 100° . The dry precipitate was finely powdered in an agate mortar and then subjected to further drying in an air-oven at 100° before transferring to sample tubes.

The samples thus obtained were analysed for Fe^{+++} , Fe^{++} , AsO_4^{3-} and AsO_3^{3-} by the same process of analysis as was followed in the case of the precipitate obtained by mixing FeCl_3 and NaAsO_2 (vide Part II of the series).

TABLE I

	Total iron.	Fe ...	Fe ..	Total As.	AsO ₂ '	AsO ₄ ''	Colour.
1. Aq. FeSO ₄ (M/3.24) + neutral Na ₂ HAsO ₄ (M/3.23)	30.15%	12.96%	17.19%	32.7%	13.79%	52.91%	Greenish yellow.
Empirical formula : Fe ^{III} _{1.8} Fe ^{II} _{2.8} (AsO ₂) ₁ (AsO ₄) ₃							
2. Acidified FeSO ₄ (M/3.24)+ neutral Na ₂ HAsO ₄ (M/3.23)	30.86	30.83	Nil	32.8	2.45	57.59	Dull brown
Empirical formula : Fe ^{III} ₂₄ (AsO ₂) ₁ (AsO ₄) ₁₃							
3. Acidified FeSO ₄ (M/6.86)+ neutral Na ₂ HAsO ₄ (M/3.23)	32.8	32.8	Nil	30.16	1.11	54.45	Dull brown
Empirical formula : Fe ^{III} _{53.2} (AsO ₂) ₁ (AsO ₄) _{27.7}							
4. Acidified FeSO ₄ (M/5)+ neutral Na ₂ HAsO ₄ (M/5)	28.44	28.44	Nil	34.27	1.65	61.38	Dull brown
Empirical formula : Fe ^{III} _{32.9} (AsO ₂) ₁ (AsO ₄) _{23.6}							
5. Acidified FeSO ₄ (M/10)+ neutral Na ₂ HAsO ₄ (M/10)	29.66	29.66	Nil	34.87	1.79	62.27	Dull brown
Empirical formula : Fe ^{III} _{31.6} (AsO ₂) ₁ (AsO ₄) _{26.7}							

TABLE II

(Precipitated product obtained by ageing)

	Total iron.	Fe ...	Fe ..	Total As.	AsO ₂ '	AsO ₄ ''	Colour.
1 Acidified FeSO ₄ (M/3.24)+ neutral Na ₂ HAsO ₄ (M/3.23)	31.05%	24.84%	6.21%	35.5%	Nil	65.79%	Dull brown
Empirical formula : Fe ^{III} ₄ Fe ^{II} (AsO ₄) _{4.24}							
2 Acidified FeSO ₄ (M/5)+ neutral Na ₂ HAsO ₄ (M/5)	32.7	26.14	6.58	26.8	Nil	49.66	Dull brown
Empirical formula : Fe ^{III} ₄ Fe ^{II} (AsO ₄) ₃ .							
3 Acidified FeSO ₄ (M/10)+ neutral Na ₂ HAsO ₄ (M/10)	30.93	28.78	2.15	30.87	Nil	57.22	Dull brown
Empirical Formula : Fe ^{III} _{13.4} Fe ^{II} (AsO ₄) _{10.7}							

DISCUSSION

The main points to be observed in the tables are :—

(a) The variations in the total iron content in the samples, prepared under different conditions of acidity and dilution of the reactants, do not exceed 4.40% ; variation of total arsenic is 4.6% only.

(b) The proportions of arsenate and arsenite, and ferric and ferrous change at random.

(c) The composition becomes more similar by the ageing method.

The analytical results can be interpreted on the basis of mutual oxidation and reduction of the reactants. Arsenic acid is stronger than arsenious acid. Hence the arsenate product should suffer less hydrolysis than iron arsenite, and this is supported by simultaneous increase in the proportion of Fe and AsO_4'' . H_3AsO_4 is much more soluble than H_3AsO_3 or HAsO_2 , and hence the proportionate increase of $(\text{AsO}_4)''$ with increase of Fe suggests that H_3AsO_4 is not in the free state but in the form of ferric or ferrous arsenate.

When the iron arsenate is prepared by ageing the mixture of reactants, their mutual oxidation and reduction, and adsorption attain a maximum, and hence the composition becomes more similar. The arsenite formed by mutual oxidation and reduction is slowly oxidised to arsenate on ageing, and therefore the resulting compound contains ferrous, ferric and arsenate components only.

In view of the above observations, it can be concluded that there is a similarity between the mechanism of reaction between a ferric salt and sodium arsenite, and that of a ferrous salt and sodium arsenate. It is not possible, however, to work out their exact molecular formulae by purely analytical methods on account of their hydrolytic and adsorptive properties.

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